

**THE ISSUE OF EMPLOYMENT FOR GRADUATES IN IMPROVING THE
MECHANISM OF COMPETITIVENESS OF REGIONAL HIGHER
EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS**

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Abstract

The article analyzes the urgent issue of solving the issue of providing employment to graduates in the regions in order to improve the mechanism of managing the competitiveness of HEIs.

Keywords

Education, graduate, demand, supply, modern profession, pedagogue.

In today's era of globalization, it is important to ensure the competitiveness of higher education institutions and to improve the management mechanism in this matter. In this regard, employment of graduates of educational institutions is one of the acute and serious problems of the labor market in our country. One side of the problem is employers and their demand for quality, competitive personnel, and the other side is the problem of unemployment in the country, which affects even graduates of higher education institutions. On the third hand, it is a fact that the rapid development of information technologies and robotics in the world will cross the issue of unemployment for Uzbekistan as well.

In 2019, it was held in the world experienceThe coronavirus pandemic has encouraged young people in our country, especially graduates of higher education institutions, to demand quantitative and qualitative changes in the labor market. The issue of employment of graduates is inextricably linked with the real sector of the country's economy.

The main improvement of the mechanism of management of competitiveness of higher educational institutionsone of its goals is the issue of employment of graduates of higher education institutions, the practical result of which is to develop a methodology of quantitative and qualitative collective research based on the requirements of the labor market. Based on it, along with the supply of specialized personnel suitable for the labor market demand of Uzbekistan and the

countries of the world, expansion of training of specialized personnel with strong demand will be launched.

Research work on the above issue is carried out in the following stages:

- Expected results and their significance (expected results and their scientific and social significance;
- compliance of the planned results with the results of world-class research 4
- possibilities of implementation of planned results in the economic and social spheres in the future.

It is known that today, the issue of providing employment to graduates is one of the most pressing issues in the countries of the world, including Uzbekistan, and the solution of which is becoming more and more difficult day by day. The issue of finding a job and training the young generation graduating from a higher education institution can be solved in several ways. The most effective of them is the elimination of problems in the development of quantitative and qualitative integrated research methodology for evaluating the system of employment of graduates of higher education institutions. These include large-scale practices such as extensive literature reviews, peer review, and pilot studies. These approaches are the existing methodologies, tools used in evaluating graduate employability, their advantages and disadvantages, best practices from other studies are also explored. This in turn increases the stability of the methodology to be developed while helping to avoid duplication of work that has already been done.

The following sample projects will be developed in the development of quantitative and qualitative integrated research methodology for evaluating the employment system of graduates of higher education institutions:

- The specific characteristics of the Fergana Valley, the region where the methodology is applied, are studied, the demand and supply of the labor market, the economic situation, the fields of activity and the technology of studying regional needs;
- Involvement of interested parties, that is, cooperation with local higher education institutions, for example, TATU Fergana branch, employers, government agencies and other interested parties will be established. The development of this methodology takes into account the opinions of interested parties;
- When creating adaptation and modification technology, it is taken into account that different institutions, specialties, industries and regions differ;
- Available resources such as budget, personnel, technical infrastructure and expertise are analyzed. These resources are taken into account in the development

of the methodology so that implementation in the regional context is convenient and effective.

- After the database is formed, Technical conditions and regulations will be developed for the implementation of the methodology.

In the development of quantitative and qualitative integrated research methodology for evaluating the employment system of graduates of higher education institutions, it is achieved with the help of comprehensive socio-economically effective solutions. In addition to the higher educational institution, graduate, employer, and other subjective parties related to this, it is necessary that the territorial-geographical objective parties also benefit from social and economic interests.

Although the developed methodology is planned to be developed on the example of the Fergana branch of TATU, taking into account the lack of funds, there are about 10 higher education institutions in the Fergana region, and more than 20 in the Fergana, Andijan, Namangan regions of the Fergana valley, which also have a positive effect on the issue of employment of graduates. is expected to show. For this purpose, the future plans of the project include implementation of practical tasks on the evaluation of the system of providing employment to graduates of higher education institutions at the level of the regions of the Fergana Valley. In the implementation of this task, a wide range of opportunities will be mobilized.

In the future, it is expected to conclude contracts between the interested parties regarding the supply of quality personnel.

Quantitative and qualitatively integrated studies on the evaluation of the developed system of employment of graduates of higher education institutions, based on the effectiveness of the methodology, can determine the amount of training of quality personnel based on the requirements of the State labor market and approve the work plan. That is, on the basis of the obtained preliminary scientific results, it is expected to expand the geographical area of the methodology of quantitative and qualitative integrated research on the evaluation of the system of providing employment to graduates of higher education institutions.

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